

Synthetic Seed Technology: An Overview

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Introduction

Synthetic seed is one of the most exciting methods in plant biotechnology, with the potential to be modified for horticultural and agricultural improvement in the present and future. Since all of the propagules used in synthetic seed preparation were created by in vitro clonal propagation, they did not experience two basic events of sexual reproduction: meiotic recombination (during crossing over) and gametic fusion of two separate parental genomes (cross-pollination), all of which can result in new forms of heterozygosity in zygotic plants. As a result, offspring resulting from synthetic seeds are still true to type when compared to their parent plant. Propagation by somatic embryogenesis and artificial seeds is the only way to save certain species, such as ornamental plants.

Synthetic Seed Technology

Artificially encapsulated somatic embryos, shoot buds, cell aggregates, or any other tissue that can be used for sowing as a seed and can turn into a plant under in vitro or ex vitro conditions, as well as after storage, are known as synthetic seeds. (Mudasir et al., 2017). Synthetic seed technology requires the manipulation of in vitro culture systems for large-scale production of viable materials that can convert into plants. Encapsulation, somatic embryogenesis, organogenesis, and enhanced axillary bud proliferation systems are effective techniques for rapid and large-scale in vitro multiplication of elite and desirable plant species. These systems develop a significant number of somatic embryos or shoot buds, which are used as effective planting materials for plant regeneration, either after mild treatment or without treatment with growth regulators.

Production Technology

Desiccated/Dry Synthetic Seed: Desiccated synthetic seeds are produced only in the plant species whose somatic embryos are desiccation tolerant. The schematic representation of desiccated synthetic seed production from somatic embryos are given below.

Hydrated Synthetic Seed: Hydrated seeds are formed in plants with recalcitrant somatic embryos that are vulnerable to desiccation. Synthetic seeds are created by encapsulating somatic embryos in hydrogel capsules. The schematic representation of hydrated synthetic seed production is given below.

Propagules (somatic embryo, apical bud, axillary buds, immature seed embryos, protocorm like bodies

Achievements

According to Onay et al., (1996) somatic embryos have been encapsulated to create synthetic seeds in tree species such as *santalum album*, *pistacia vera*, and *Mangifera indica*. Synthetic seed production has been recorded in a variety of cereals, tubers, tomatoes, and other commercially valuable plants such as soya bean, mustards, coffee, tobacco, and cotton (Datta et al., 1999). Bhattacharyya et al., (2018) used 3% sodium alginate and 100 mL CaCl₂ in combination with various aromatic cytokinin to encapsulate the protocorm-like bodies of Leopard orchid (*Ansellia africana*). Aromatic cytokinin paired with IBA were found to be the best formula for synthetic seed viability, with an 88%.

Implication

- 1. Propagation of recalcitrant seeds:** Using excised embryos in synthetic seeds, possibly we can increase the longevity of the recalcitrant seeds.
- 2. Propagation of seedless fruit (Grapes, watermelon):** Triploid species do not produce viable seeds for natural propagation, need to be crossed between tetraploid and diploid. Hence, synthetic seeds as propagules can be effective.
- 3. Propagation of seasonal plants:** Using synthetic seed technology, seasonal plants can be produced throughout the year.
- 4. Fast multiplication and true-to-type plants:** Suspending traditional methods (like budding, grafting) we can get true-to-type plants with larger quantities of plants round the year.
- 5. Reduces cost of production:** like in banana.

Limitations

- 1. High production cost:** The initial production and instrumentation costs are a major havoc.
- 2. Asynchronous development of somatic embryos:** Improper maturation and asynchronous developments is an issue.
- 3. Poor conversion of these artificial seeds into plantlets:** They show positive impacts in controlled atmosphere, but somehow fail to establish itself in open atmosphere.
- 4. Problems with gelling agents:** The coating acts as a hindrance, they dried out easily hence they need a humid storage condition or coated with a hydrophilic membrane which help in embryo respiration.

Conclusion

Going down the line, if this technology is efficiently-commercially exploited, then this can act as a boon to a profitable multi-billion rupees industry. Keeping in mind the setbacks, there is continuous need for improvement and implicating this technology in valuable crop plants. With subsequent developments,

synthetic seeds can be used as a medium for exchange of seeds for germplasm conservation and genetic improvement programmes.

References

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